

INDONESIAN DEFENSE STRATEGY AS AN ISLAND COUNTRY

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Abstract

Indonesia is one of the largest archipelagic countries in the world. With the composition of the region that spreads from Sabang to Merauke, making the country's resilience important to discuss. State resilience is the concept of the emergence of conditions of security and comfort on a national scale in every aspect that exists in the country. One way to maintain national resilience is through geostrategy. One of the geostrategies can be implemented in the form of geopolitics. With the development of the times, resistance to political aspects is certainly not enough, for that, there is a development called geo-economics'. Both geopolitics and geo-economics are carried out in accordance with the objectives of each country. Each country will have a different understanding of security and formulate different main goals. In discussing the concepts of geostrategy and geo-economics', of course, we will discuss the geographical conditions of the country. Indonesia with a composition of two-thirds of the ocean makes it a maritime country. The concept of Indonesia's state resilience has become the concept of maritime resilience. Maritime security is important because Indonesia relies on the sea, which balances the richness of natural resources, and makes the sea a means of communication, transportation, and defense.

Keywords: geo-economics', geopolitics, geostrategy, national resilience, maritime country

Introduction

Indonesia is one of the largest archipelagic countries in the world or commonly known as a maritime country. Its territory stretches from Sabang to Merauke and consists of various ethnic groups, religions, races, and groups. Under these conditions, the issue of state resilience becomes important to discuss. State resilience is not only the responsibility of state leaders or certain agencies, but is the responsibility of all Indonesian people. A sense of nationalism is one of the important keys in maintaining the sovereignty and integrity of a country. At present, the feeling of nationalism that is fading due to reduced public trust in the government or the division of certain groups can become a major threat to the country's resilience. For this reason, as an effort to maintain the sovereignty and integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, a national defense system that has a strong legal foundation is needed. The legal basis for the defense of the Republic of Indonesia consists of several components, namely the ideal, constitutional, juridical, historical, visional, conceptual, and doctrinal foundations (Suko, 2019).

Discussing about national security certainly does not escape the discussion on geostrategy. The geopolitical concept of Archipelago Insights is implemented as a national defense which is Indonesia's geostrategy. This is done in an effort for national, regional, and supranational defense. The Archipelago Insight is a national concept of the unity and integrity of the nation and the State of Indonesia. National Resilience is an effort to maintain that the dynamics that occur in the Indonesian State are still able to overcome the problems that occur as an effort to achieve the goals and ideals of the country.

The basic concept of Indonesian geopolitics is National Resilience with the dimension of Astagatra. This means that complex national life will be mapped in a simple way but still depicts the real national condition. Astagatra consists of two aspects, namely the Natural Trigatra and the Social Pancagatra. Natural Trigatra includes things such as geography or regional conditions, natural resources, and human resources. The social pancagatra consist of ideology, politics, economy, social and culture, as well as defense and security. The success of geostrategy is highly dependent on the country's ability to utilize its Trigatra to develop Pancagatra. It is undeniable that one measure of a country's progress is often linked and viewed from an economic point of view. For this reason, it can be said that the purpose of geopolitics is to revive the country's economy. This concept is commonly known as geoeconomics, which is a view of the economy in terms of geographical factors, both at the national, regional, and global scope.

In this study, the focus of the discussion will be on understanding the concepts of geostrategy and geopolitics, especially in Indonesia. To better understand the concepts of geostrategy and geoeconomics, there will be discussions on several related topics such as geopolitics of the Southeast Asia region, Indonesia's maritime security, national security, Indonesia as an archipelagic country and Indonesia's defense strategy in the archipelagic state. This concept is important because it relates to national resilience. With the development of the times, especially in the 20th century, changes in the economic, social, cultural, and political fields indirectly have an impact on national defense and resilience. Traditionally, the concept of defense and resilience is only viewed from a security perspective. The development of the times has changed the view and understanding to be out in all directions. Given the importance of national resilience, the concepts of geostrategy and geoeconomics are important to be discussed and understood.

Research methods

In this study, the method used is SLR (Systematic Literature Reviews), which is a systematic and thorough literature study, starting from literature search, critical analysis and review, and evaluation of the data found in the literature. This study uses a qualitative method, namely drawing conclusions based on literature studies conducted using secondary data in the form of books, journals, and websites. All sources used are accessed through electronic media.

Results and Discussion

An understanding of the concepts of geopolitics and geoeconomics can be obtained through a discussion of Indonesia's national defense strategy, especially as a maritime country, and an understanding of geopolitics in the Southeast Asia region, the region where Indonesia is located. Every aspect discussed will have continuity with each other which if understood properly will give birth to an understanding of the concepts of geostrategy and geopolitics.

1. Geopolitics of the Southeast Asian Region

Southeast Asia is a part of Asia which is geographically located in the southeastern part of India, south to southwest China, and northwest of Australia (Singh, 2007). Southeast Asia is divided into two regions, namely mainland Southeast Asia and Archipelago Southeast Asia. The areas included in mainland Southeast Asia include parts of China which are located south of the Panjang River, Myanmar, Indochina, Peninsular Malaysia, and Indonesia. Archipelagic Southeast Asia itself consists of Indonesia, East Malaysia, the Philippines, Taiwan, and Brunei Darussalam. If we talk about Southeast Asia, then one of the countries that does not escape the discussion is of course China. China is one of the countries that has economic power and has a lot of influence on the economic system in several countries and even the world.

Geopolitics is the implementation of a country's politics that is influenced by its geographical conditions. Even though they are in the same region, namely Southeast Asia, each country will definitely have differences in terms of geography which indirectly affects the policies that the country takes in an effort to achieve the country's goals. This goal can be achieved by using geostrategy. The Silk Road, also known as the Silk Road, is China's first geostrategic idea that considers geographical aspects. The Silk Road was a trade route created by the Chinese government with the main commodity being silk. After the Silk Road was vacuumed because it was closed by the Ottoman Empire, then China made a new trade route, namely The New Silk Road, known as OBOR (One Belt One Road). The OBOR policy was made by China as one of the steps to achieve its political interests. Cooperation and investment arising from the emergence of this policy will be a way for China to strengthen its relations with other countries, especially countries in the Southeast Asia region. With the breadth of coverage in OBOR, it will also give the impression that China is a big country, which indirectly improves its face in the international world. When China was under Xi Jinping's rule, he built the concept of the "Chinese Dream" which is a vision for the Chinese people to achieve prosperity and make their nation a nation that is reckoned with by the world. Unlike China, Indonesia's geopolitical concept does not aim to show its power or strength to other countries. The concept of Indonesia's geopolitics was born from Pancasila as an ideology whose main purpose is to maintain the unity and integrity of the nation, maintain national identity, and maintain the survival of the nation and state. Even though they are in the same area, in fact the geopolitical concepts adopted by China and Indonesia are much different. This goes back to the geographical conditions, including the resources owned, the foundation, and the ideals of the country.

In the course of the times, the world's focus has changed, not only in the defense aspect but also in the economic aspect. Economic strength becomes an important aspect of the continuity of a country which then gives rise to a concept called geoeconomics. OBOR also appears as one of China's efforts in managing its resources for the benefit of the country's economy. The construction of this trade route is an effort to establish cooperation with countries in Southeast Asia, including Indonesia. Economic development is an important point for China. China considers that economic development is a foundation for building a prosperous and strong country. Even now, China's economic interests are the main focus.

In order to improve its economy, China has invited several countries to cooperate with their countries so that they have guaranteed market access and resources. Most of China's trade is carried out through the South China Sea, Indian Ocean, and the Malacca Strait. Access to sea trade is apparently not good enough for China because it takes a long time and is prone to piracy. To overcome this problem, China opened a land trade route that would connect several important cities in Asia and Europe with China. Although developing land trade routes, China still pays attention to its sea trade routes, OBOR. OBOR is an important project because it will open China's access to the Southeast Asian economic zone. This policy is considered by the United States as a policy that "traps" poor countries. For Indonesia itself, of course, it must study more about this policy so as not to create an increasing debt. As it is known that currently Indonesia's debt to China continues to increase every year due to this OBOR project.

2. Indonesian Maritime Security

With the configuration of the Indonesian state which consists of many islands and 2/3 of them are oceans, of course Indonesia's maritime security is an important aspect. With the total number of islands in Indonesia reaching 17,500 islands, Indonesia's maritime security requires a large portion, ranging from funding, strategy, law, to human resources. Every country certainly has national interests to be achieved. The concept of maritime security then emerged as an effort to achieve Indonesia's national interests, as a large maritime country. Maritime security is a small part of national security.

World trade is dominated by trade by sea, therefore marine security is an important aspect that must be implemented. For Indonesia, the sea plays an important role, at least the sea plays a role as a unifying medium for the Indonesian territory, a means of transportation and communication, natural resources that play a role in supporting the economy, and as a defense medium. Marine security has a goal to protect Indonesian seas from things such as threats of territorial violations from other countries, illegal exploitation of natural resources in Indonesian seas and environmental pollution, dangers of shipping navigation, and other violations of law. Illegal exploitation, for example, cannot be underestimated. Indonesia is an archipelagic country where many people depend on their livelihoods from natural resources in the sea. Overexploitation of the sea, let alone destroying marine ecosystems and existing seeds, will certainly affect the survival of fishermen who depend on marine products for their livelihood. Then illegal fishing is also an incident that needs to be dealt with firmly. The declining marine products of several countries are not impossible to encourage them to fish in Indonesia's rich seas. In fact, this action will certainly harm Indonesia. With weak maritime resilience, this will always be a way for other countries to take advantage of Indonesia's seas. Another threat that is also dangerous is the smuggling of narcotics through Indonesian waters. These things will happen when Indonesia's maritime resilience is weak.

The sea is the main guard that needs to be secured in an effort to secure land areas. One of the issues that threatens maritime Indonesia today is about illegal fishing. One of the efforts to maintain Indonesia's maritime security is the establishment of Bakamla (Sea Security Agency). Bakamla will be one of the institutions that will assist the Navy to maintain the security and safety of the coast, as well as enforce the sovereignty of the waters. Bakamla was inaugurated

in 2014 and coordinated directly with the Coordinating Minister for Political, Legal and Security Affairs who also coordinated with the Coordinating Minister for Maritime Affairs. Bakamla is tasked with conducting patrols in Indonesian waters to ensure security and safety. Bakamla's function is to guard, supervise, and follow up on law violations that occur in Indonesian waters. In addition, Bakamla is also tasked with seeking help if search assistance is needed in Indonesian waters.

Another policy is Government Regulation Number 16 of 2017 concerning Indonesian Marine Policy, one of which is Indonesia's step to become the World Maritime Axis as aspired by President Joko Widodo and to utilize Indonesia's marine resources as much as possible for the benefit of the people's prosperity.

The sea has boundaries that are not "clear" different from the land. Therefore, the threats that can arise are quite large and require good handling. Not only during the Joko Widodo administration, several policies regarding the sea have also been issued since the reign of President Soekarno. During the Soekarno government, he issued a policy regarding Indonesia's maritime boundaries through the Juanda Declaration. The contents of the declaration are certainly a breath of fresh air for Indonesia's seas because the previous policies brought many losses and threats to Indonesia's sovereignty.

Then during the reign of Abdurrahman Wahid, for the first time the Ministry of Maritime Affairs was formed as a form of attention to Indonesian maritime affairs. This policy was then continued by the next president, Megawati Soekarnoputri, by making the Indonesian Navy (Navy) a major force in the region and increasing the strength of the marines. Then during the reign of Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono, he strengthened the Navy. All the steps taken by both past and current leaders are an effort to safeguard and maintain Indonesia's maritime security for the progress of Indonesia, both economically and politically.

3. National Security

The state has a duty to maintain the safety of all levels of society and its territory. Initially the concept of safety was defined as a safe condition and a sense of security from outside interference. But along with the times, it turns out that the threats that come not only from outside but from within the people themselves can encourage the division of the nation. Security can be achieved when the creation of safe conditions and a sense of security on a large scale covers the entire country, including the entire territory of the people, which is known as national security. National security covers the whole of a country including its territory and all the resources contained therein, and all its people and interests. The concept of national security has been put forward by A. H. Nasution since the 1960s. Each country will have a different concept of national security because the definition of security itself can vary, depending on how each country defines it, also the conditions experienced by each country are different. Frederick H. Hartmann stated that "Concepts of national security will vary from state to state on proportion to the concept of vital national interests". This means that the definition of state security will vary according to the main national interests of the country.

National security does not only include security from external threats, the security in question is security from all kinds of aspects. National security is the security of national goals, national values, territory, population, natural and artificial resources, national wealth, and state information. In the traditional interpretation, state security is only defined as a condition that is free from external threats. Maybe some security is still foreign to our ears, for example the security of national goals. The national goals of each country will of course be different depending on the conditions of each country. With the changing world and the increasingly dense population in the world, it is increasingly difficult for everyone to meet their daily needs. Even though they have different national goals, approximately the national goals of each country will lead to meeting the needs of its people so that all the people of that country can live in peace and serenity, as well as preventing international conflicts. Then another example is the security of noble values. Each country holds a noble value that will be used as a guide in carrying out state life. Losing noble values will certainly have an impact on the erosion of national identity or identity which will gradually erode the sense of nationalism that will undermine a country. Next is the security of the nation's wealth. The wealth referred to here refers to historical objects such as inscriptions, or temples which are relics of a country. These objects are historical objects that need to be protected so that they are not claimed, taken, or damaged by other nations. By guarding it, citizens indirectly participate in remembering and appreciating the history of their own nation. Then no less important is the security of state information. Many countries are trying to "steal" the information of a country with a specific purpose which is certainly detrimental to the country. Keeping confidential or archival information is important as one of the steps to maintain national security.

In order to maintain national security, a certain level of national stability is needed. National stability covers broad matters following a dynamic world change, stability in question is stability in terms of politics, economy, social and culture as well as defense and security. State stability can be achieved by establishing laws or policies, both written and unwritten. Unfortunately, at present the threats that arise for the stability of the country are mostly not threats from outside, or from other countries. Many internal threats have emerged which have destabilized the country's stability. The emergence of groups or groups that are contrary to the concept of Indonesian ideology can be a source of dangerous threats to Indonesia. With the area being spread widely, it will be very difficult for Indonesia to control every movement of the existing community. For this reason, maintaining state stability is very important and attention and intervention from local governments is needed so that all these internal threats can be avoided. This internal threat usually arises because there is a group of people with certain positions who carry out a provocation that eventually gives birth to a group that is not nationalist. Steps that can be taken to prevent the emergence of separatism are to instill nationalism and love for the country from an early age. It also requires an understanding of the concept of state ideology so that people know what is the guideline in carrying out a good and right state life as one way to achieve the goals of the Indonesian state. The involvement of all parties is very much needed in order to achieve an advanced Indonesia both in terms of economy, social, culture, and politics.

4. Indonesia as an Archipelago Country

After World War II, legal developments required each country to expand its power in the sea bordering the country's coast. Each country tries to widen its sea area to the high seas due to the encouragement of political, economic, defense and security factors. Indonesia as one of the largest archipelagic countries must of course change its provisions regarding marine areas as an effort to safeguard national interests. In the past, the applicable law of the sea was the Territorial Zee en Maritieme Kringen Ordonantie (1939). In this provision, it is regulated that the width of the territorial sea is 3 nautical miles measured from the lowest waterline of the islands included in the territory of Indonesia. These provisions were valid until 1957. In its development, following the changing times, these provisions were replaced by new provisions which were considered more in line with the interests of the Indonesian state. One thing that is no longer relevant is that such a measurement method will create a separate sea area between the Indonesian islands and there are parts of the high seas that will endanger Indonesia's sovereignty. Such a form of the sea will complicate the process of controlling the sea from businesses that may harm Indonesia, such as smuggling and others. From an economic point of view, such a calculation of the sea area is also detrimental to Indonesia because it allows other countries to catch fish in the seas around the Indonesian coast. From the political aspect, of course, the separated sea areas can give rise to a separatist movement due to the separate areas which will endanger the integrity of the nation.

Therefore, a new provision was made which was issued on December 13, 1957 and known as the Djuanda Declaration, the contents of which more or less stated that every waters around, between, and connecting islands or parts of islands that are still included in the land area of the Republic of Indonesia with ignoring the extent and width of the sea is part of Indonesia's national waters which are under the sovereignty of the Republic of Indonesia. Then traffic for foreign ships on these waters is allowed as long as it does not conflict with the sovereignty and safety of the Unitary Republic of Indonesia. Then to determine the territorial boundaries are 12 miles wide from the outermost boundaries of the islands of the Republic of Indonesia. This became known as the Archipelago Insight, a conception that aims to safeguard national interests and the territorial integrity of the country. This conception is strengthened by Law No. 4 Prp. 1960.

These new provisions then gave birth to the concept of an archipelagic state, namely a country whose entire territory consists of one or more islands. As one of the archipelagic countries, there are obligations that must be fulfilled by countries that have the status of archipelagic countries, including those countries must respect the applicable international agreements, also respect the legitimate activities of neighboring countries side by side, as well as respect the rights of other countries. - traditional fishing rights.

5. Indonesia's Defense Strategy in the Field of Archipelagic Countries

Currently, Indonesia is in the era of President Joko Widodo's administration. The 7th President of the Republic of Indonesia pays great attention to Indonesian waters and wants to make it a PMD (World Maritime Axis). Several strategies carried out by the government for the defense

of Indonesia in the field of archipelagic countries include internal and external efforts, namely the development of maritime infrastructure, upholding the sovereignty of the maritime territory of the Republic of Indonesia, revitalizing marine economic sectors, strengthening maritime connectivity, and increasing the quality and quantity of natural resources. marine man.

If you pay attention to several maritime countries such as the United States of America or Britain, then the maritime defense strategy is closely related to the Navy strategy. The Navy can be a source of government strength in maintaining maritime security. For this reason, the strategies that Indonesia can do in the context of its maritime defense include increasing both the quantity and quality of the Indonesian Navy. Of course, this must be accompanied by government policies that support matters for Indonesia's maritime development. One of the right steps that Indonesia has taken in protecting Indonesia's maritime territory was during the reign of the Minister of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries from the 2014-2019 Working Cabinet, Susi Pudjiastuti. Various firm policies taken by Minister Susi Pudjiastuti, such as the sinking of foreign vessels fishing in the Indonesian area and the ban on the export of lobster seeds, have become a good breakthrough that not only protects Indonesia's maritime sovereignty, but also protects and maintains the continuity of natural resources in Indonesian seas. A fairly simple policy, namely the sinking of foreign ships that cross Indonesian waters, is in fact a smart move that can indirectly be done to maintain the security of Indonesia's seas. Foreign ships fishing in Indonesian waters could be spies of foreign countries that could interfere with Indonesia's sovereignty. Simple and concrete steps are in fact needed as a strategy for securing Indonesia's seas in the future. As is known, that actually Indonesia does not lack human resources to "guard" the Indonesian seas. However, it is often rogue elements who allow foreign ships to escape which can become seeds that damage Indonesia's maritime security. The sea is a source of livelihood for most of the Indonesian people. The sea provides a livelihood for Indonesia. The sea can be said to be a benchmark for Indonesia's progress. Advancing Indonesia's seas means advancing Indonesia. Sea management and guarding that is not strict or wrong will cause national security to be shaken because in essence maritime security is part of national security. Maintaining national security can be started from maintaining maritime security.

Conclusions, Recommendations and Limitations

Conclusion

Each country will have a different concept of national security depending on the main goals of the country. Indonesia as a country based on Pancasila has the main goal of maintaining unity and integrity. Therefore, in practice all policies made will try to support the achievement of these goals. One of the steps to achieve national security is to maintain state resilience. State resilience can be achieved by implementing geopolitics which is part of geostrategy. With the development of the times, geoeconomics emerged as a development to complement geopolitics. As a maritime country, maritime resilience means national resilience because the sea is the main gate that can be a place for threats both internal and external to enter.

Recommendations and Restrictions

To achieve an Indonesian state that has strong national resilience, it is necessary to have an attitude of nationalism in every Indonesian nation. The various ethnic groups, races, religions, and groups that exist in Indonesia can be a source of division for the Indonesian nation. However, if all the children of the nation are willing to work together and make these differences into strengths, then it is not impossible that Indonesia will become a country with strong political and economic defenses. Basically, the progress of a nation is not only determined by the current government or certain agencies, but requires the cooperation of all elements of society in the country. Then, firmness is needed in implementing existing policies because any good policy that is not implemented properly will not produce good results. According to Hakim (2021), the Archipelago State Defense Military Strategy covers at least five things, namely: First, the TD (Total Defense) system must include NE (National Education) and NS (National Service). Second, the strategy also breaks down to the weapon system. Third, the strategy must cover the Territory of Sovereignty. Fourth, the strategy also has a War Force Design. Finally, fifth, there is a Unified Command.

Hakim's offer (2021) regarding the Military Strategy for the Defense of the Archipelago State can be an alternative solution in the context of accelerating the realization of the PMD (World Maritime Axis) announced by President Joko Widodo, as well as being a defense strategy for Indonesia as an archipelagic country.

In this discussion, the problems discussed are only problems that exist in Indonesia. Then in the discussion of geopolitics in Southeast Asia, China is used as a reference because it is one of the influential countries both on the scale of Southeast Asia and on the international scene.

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